

The Impact UEFA's FFP regulations on Audit Fees. Evidence from Spanish Football

Mercedes Mareque^a, Angel Barajas^a and Francisco López-Corrales^b

^aFaculty of Business and Tourism, University of Vigo, Campus Universitario, 32004 Ourense, Spain, Email: chedesmareque@uvigo.es, ^bSt. Petersburg School of Economics and Management, St. Petersburg, 194100, Russia 3, Kantemirovskaya ul. Email: balonso@hse.ru; ^bFaculty of Social Sciences and Communication, University of Vigo, Campus A Xunqueira, 36005 Pontevedra, Spain, Email: corrales@uvigo.es

ABSTRACT

Research question: this paper analyzes if the Financial Fair Play regulations set by UEFA have had influenced the auditing fees charged to the football clubs. In addition, the determinants of audit fees have being explored.

Research methods: two-sample t test with equal variances has been used in order to determine if there are significant differences. Later, a panel data regression with clubs fix effect has been carried out to estimate the determinants of audit fees in clubs de football.

Results and findings: there has been an increase of audit fees after the implementation of FFP regulations. On top of that, audit fees are explained by the presence of foreign investors, if the audit firm is one of the Big4 and if the auditor is a woman.

Keywords: Football, Audit fees, regulation, Fair Play, UEFA

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Introduction

Financial situation of most of European football clubs has been characterized by their increasing debts and persistent deficits (García & Rodríguez, 2003; Barajas, 2004; Ascari & Gagnepain, 2006; Boscá, Liern, Martínez & Sala, 2008; Gay, 2009a, 2009b; Barajas y Rodríguez, 2010; Gammelsaeter, 2010; Storm & Nielsen, 2012; Deloitte, 2014; Robinson & Simmons, 2014). European football has been affected by serious financial problems due to the unbalance between revenues and expenses, and the subsequent increase of debt. For that reason, some clubs are to the verge of bankruptcy. There have been a high number of clubs under administration. Kuper & Szymanski (2009) remark that 40 English professional football clubs have been involved in processes of insolvency between 1992 and 2008. Beech, Horsman & Magraw (2010) point out that among the clubs in the Premier League and the English Football League Championship in season 2008-09, more than the half had passed through a process of insolvency in the last years. In Spain at the end of 2011, 22 clubs were or had been under administration (Barajas & Rodríguez, 2014)¹.

The Union of European Football Associations (UEFA), concerned about the financial health of the clubs, approved the Financial Fair Play (FFP) Regulations in 2010. It was updated in 2012 and 2015. Since 2011, all clubs that take part in competitions organized by UEFA have to fulfil the requirements of the FFP. These regulations aim to ensure the long-term financial viability and the sustainability of the clubs. They should be managed in break even, avoid reporting negative equity changes, set overdue payables and finally to prove their going concern ability (UEFA, 2010; Morrow, 2014).

The FFP Regulation set that the financial statements of clubs have to be audited by an independent external auditor². UEFA will assess the content of the auditing report and can deny the license if³ (i) the report has a disclaimer of opinion or an adverse opinion, (ii) the auditor's report has either an emphasis of matter or a qualified 'except for' opinion in respect of going concern, (iii) the auditor's report has, in respect of a matter other than going concern, either an emphasis of matter or a qualified 'except for'

¹ This is a situation similar to the one defined by chapter 11 of bankruptcy in USA.

² Spanish Sport Law (*Ley 10/1990*) says that Clubs and Sporting Companies (*Sociedades Anónimas Deportivas*) will have to present the audited financial statement to the Spanish Superior Council of Sport and La Liga before depositing them in the Companies House (*Registro Mercantil*).

³ See Annex IX of FFP Regulations 2015.

opinion but they are significant to express the true and fair image of the equity and financial results of the club.

Failure by the clubs of the criteria established by the FFP Regulation may lead to sanctions and the license for participation in UEFA competitions may be denied. This could lead to serious losses to the sanctioned club, since competitions such as the Champions League or the Europa League provide significant revenues to clubs, which could jeopardize their financial viability (Dimitropoulos, 2016).

The role of auditors is going to become still more relevant. Their responsibility in expressing their opinion is going to increase as well as the auditing effort due to the financial problems that clubs are experiencing. The relevance of having an unqualified opinion can bring pressing on the auditor. Ruiz-Barbadillo (2016) asserts that the meaning of an unqualified opinion for the users can generate an extra cost for the company and its managers. This fact can imply pressing on the auditor to provide a positive opinion what is a threat for the independency of the auditor. This possible attitude can damage the interest of the shareholder, on top of being a fraud, and could affect to the stakeholders that use the financial information (De Angelo, 1982; Archambeault & DeZoort, 2001; Ruiz-Barbadillo & Gómez-Aguilar, 2007).

On the other hand, the weak financial position of numerous football clubs, some of them with serious problems on going concern, will increase the risk of the auditors and it will affect their work. The studies of Simunic (1980), Simunic & Stein (1996), Seetharaman, Gul, & Lynn (2002), Choi Kim, Liu, & Simunic (2008) and Francis & Wang (2008) support the theory that auditors increase their effort in high risk environment. If the perception of risk in the company is higher the auditors increase the audit procedures which imply more evidences to gather, more time, more personal and, in consequence, higher fees (Mautz & Sharaf, 1961; Davis, Ricchiute & Trompeter, 1993; Bell, Wayne & Shackelford, 2001; Bell, Doogar & Solomon, 2008; Bedard, Donald, Curtis & Jenkins, 2008; Asthana, Balsam & Kim, 2009; Redmayne, Bradbury & Cahan, 2010).

Griffin, Lont & Sun (2009), Vieru & Shadewitz (2010), Kim, Liu, & Zheng (2012), De George, Ferguson & Spear (2013), De Fuentes & Sierra-Grau (2015a), Higgins, Lont, & Scott (2016), Lin & Yen (2016) have studied the impact of new rules or changes in regulation on audit fees in several countries from an accountancy viewpoint. Menon & Williams (2001), Informe Oxera (2006), Raghunandan & Rama (2006), Griffin & Lont (2007), Ghosh & Pawlewicz (2009), Huang, Liu, Raghunandan & Rama

(2009), Salman & Carson (2009), Charles, Glover & Sharp (2010), De Fuentes & Sierra-Grau (2015b) have analyzed the impact of changes in auditing standards on audit fees. However, there is no paper that analyzes the impact of implementation of FFP Regulations on the audit fees charged by auditors of football clubs. This paper aims to fill this gap in the literature. To study this, the Spanish clubs in First Division during the period 2007 to 2016 have been used as sample to test it. So, from 2007 to 2010 there were no regulations, from 2010 to 2013 it was a transition period and from 2014 to 2016 the regulations were totally implemented. Moreover, the factors that determine the audit fees are going to be studied.

There are two main contributions. First, the paper examines one of the economic consequences of the implementation of FFP regulations analyzing their effect on audit fees. Second, the behavior of audit fees are analyzed in a particular context, the football industry.

The methodology employed is in line with previous studies. After a t-test to analyze if there are significant changes in the audit fees, an OLS is used to test the hypothesis that the change in regulation and other variables affect the audit fees. Features related to both the auditor and the clubs are included in the model.

As it was said, the paper analyzes the clubs in the Spanish First Division. Those clubs can qualify to UEFA competitions (Champions League and Europa League) and they would need the UEFA license for that reason. The study period start in season 2007-2008 until 2015-16. There are three periods: Pre-FFP, it is the time before the regulations were set (since June 2007 to 2010); trans-FFP, it is a transitory period (since June 2010 to 2013); and FFP, when the regulations fully apply (since June 2013 to 2016). Similar divisions have been employed by Dimitropoulos (2016) and Dimitropoulos, Leventis & Dedoulis (2016).

The results come to demonstrate that the new rules of FFP have increased the audit fees. Moreover, audit fees are explained by the presence of foreign investors, if the audit firm is one of the Big4 and if the auditor is a woman.

Literature review and research questions

The impact of regulations in audit fees

The literature evidences that the implementation and changes in rules of both accountancy and auditing have driven to increases in the audit fees. Changes in account

rules affect the audit fees because auditors will need to invest to acquire the needed knowledge on the new rules. This will increase their cost. Moreover, the inherent risk of the financial statements will increase, and subsequently the audit risk. According to Fuentes & Sierra-Grau (2015a), IFRSs implied for most European countries a significant change in the financial statements compared to the previous accounting regulation, despite the fact that the harmonization process had already begun with the Directives 4th, 7th and 8th. These authors carried out a study trying to analyze trends in audit and non-audit fees between 2003 and 2009 in order to identify the impact of IFRS in Spain. Their results show that between 2004-2006, audit fees increased for the group accounts of listed companies, relating this increase to the incremental costs associated with the mandatory adoption of IFRS. On the other hand, there is an increase in 2008 for parent company audit fees associated with the new domestic accounting rules.

Griffin et al. (2009) examine the effects of overseas and local governance regulatory changes on the audit and non-audit fees of New Zealand audit firms over 2002–2007. They found that the audit and non-audit fees paid by New Zealand public companies to their auditors did not change appreciably in 2002–2003. However, for New Zealand companies, the audit fees increased significantly in the year prior to IFRS adoption, the year of adoption, and in subsequent years. Higgins et al. (2016) confirm the results obtained Griffin et al. (2009) that there are higher audit fees post-IFRS, but extend prior analysis by considering a longer sample period (2002-2012).

Vieru & Shadewitz (2010) studying a sample of Finnish listed firms that adopted IFRS for the first-time, analyze, how a major accounting change from local GAAP to IFRS affects the audit and non-audit fees paid to auditors. Their results indicate that IFRS adjustments, as a measure of the disparity between Finnish Accounting Standards (FAS) and IFRS, positively and significantly affect total audit fees paid to statutory auditors.

Kim et al. (2012) examine the impact of IFRS on audit fees using audit fee data from 14 EU countries that mandated IFRS adoption in 2005 for the period 2005-2008. They conclude that mandatory IFRS adoption leads to an increase in audit fees, which suggests that the increase in audit task complexity is the driving force behind the IFRS-related audit fee increase

In Australia, De George et al. (2013) using a comprehensive dataset of all publicly traded Australian companies, provide evidence of a directly observable and significant cost of IFRS adoption. They quantify an economy-wide increase in the mean level of

audit costs of 23 percent in the year of IFRS transition and estimate an abnormal IFRS-related increase in audit costs in excess of 8 percent, beyond the normal yearly fee increases in the pre-IFRS period. The results imply an overall increase in the average level of audit fees in the year of IFRS adoption of approximately 9 percent.

Lin & Yen (2016) examine audit fees from 4,129 sample observations that issued A-shares in the Shanghai and Shenzhen stock exchanges from 2005 to 2008, with the aim to empirically test the association between audit premiums and auditors' and auditees' IFRS experience. The results were that auditors with IFRS experience charged significantly higher audit premiums in the initial years of IFRS adoption, and also find that audit clients' with IFRS experience paid significantly lower incremental fees. In the UK, the Oxera (2006) report identifies high audit fees between 2002 and 2004, due to changes in regulation and accounting rules.

Regarding auditing rules, Menon & Williams (2001) observed an increase in audit fees between 1980 and 1997. The increase was more pronounced in the 1980s, remaining relatively stable in the 1990s. Most important, a significant increase was noted in 1988, when the Auditing Standards Board issued the “expectation gap” standards. Most of the research is focused on the implementation of the Sarbanes Oxley Act (SOX), which revealed high audit fees charged to customers during the post-SOX period in relation to the pre-SOX period as consequence of the increased auditing procedures, increased liability litigation and a more highly regulated audit environment.

Thus, for the United States, Raghunandan & Rama (2006) examine the association between audit fees and internal control disclosures made pursuant to Section 404 of the Sarbanes-Oxley Act and Auditing Standard No. 2 (PCAOB, 2004), which require management and the auditor to report on internal controls over financial reporting. They find that the mean (median) audit fees for the firms for fiscal 2004 is 86 percent higher than the corresponding fees for fiscal 2003. Griffin & Lont (2007) analyze audit fees following SOX for a sample of companies between 2000 and 2004. In particular, they analyze the residual increase in audit fees controlling for those factors predicted to change such fees but for the Act, finding significant relations between residual audit fees and incremental audit risk, audit effort, and auditor changes. These factors were noticeably more influential in the period following SOX.

Huang et al. (2009) examine audit fees for clients changing auditors in 2001 and 2006. They find that there is a significant initial-year audit fee discount in 2001 for clients of the Big 4 audit firms. The new clients pay, on average, about 24 percent less

than continuing clients. In contrast, there is a significant premium for new Big 4 clients in 2006. Initial-year clients pay, on average, a premium of 16 percent more than continuing clients.

Charles et al. (2010) investigate whether the association between financial reporting risk and audit fees changed during 2000–2003. They find a positive statistically and economically significant relationship between financial reporting risk and audit fees paid to Big 4 auditors. The relation between financial reporting risk and audit fees strengthened significantly in 2002 and 2003, consistent with a shift in the way auditors priced risk, likely in response to the events surrounding the Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002.

De Fuentes & Sierra-Grau (2015b) conduct a study in order to provide a comprehensive review of the literature that links auditor's industry specialization and audit fees. They find that their results are more robust for US-based studies, results are homogeneous in the post-SOX period, probably as a result of increased demand for specialized auditors.

In Nueva, Zelanda, Ghosh & Pawlewicz (2009) examine changes in auditor fees around the Sarbanes-Oxley Act. Using a wide sample between 2000 and 2005, they find a large increase in audit fees following SOX. Controlling for other auditor and client characteristics, their results suggest that average audit fees increased by approximately 74 percent following SOX.

Salman & Carson (2009) studied assesses the impact of the SOX legislation on non-US firms by examining audit fees for Australian firms with foreign registrant status in the US from 2001 to 2005, compared with audit fees for other Australian firms. The findings indicate that Australian companies issuing American Depositary Receipts (ADRs) incurred substantial increases in audit fees and Australian firms subject to the full provisions of SOX incurred larger increases in audit fees.

Therefore, according to the previous evidences, audit fees are expected to increase with the establishment of the FFP regulation due to the greater auditing effort that auditors are going to perform, and to the greater exposure of their responsibility to the time to give their opinion. Consequently, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H₁: Auditors increase their audit fees after implementing the Fair Play regulation when compared to the previous period.

The model

The model proposed by Simunic (1980) is the starting point for literature on the study of fees. In this seminal work, audit fees are considered as a cost of the clients accounting system, which they try to minimize. From this study, authors like Simunic, (1984), Chan, Ezzamel & Gwilliam (1993), Anderson & Zeghan (1994), Whisenant, Sankaraguruswamy & Raghunandan (2003) and Al-Harshani (2008) have continued to work on the topic by proposing audit fee models similar to Simunic's model.

The research conducted so far in different countries remarks that there are a set of independent variables related to the determination of audit fees for both the audited company and the auditor. The variables related to the audited company are fundamentally its size, complexity and risk. The quality of the auditor would be fundamentally the variable linked to the audit firm. Although this variable has different proxies that measure auditor quality, in most studies this variable is represented by its size (Big N) (Simunic, 1984; Gerrard, Houghton & Woodliff, 1994; DeFond, Francis & Wong, 2000; Jaramillo, García-Benau & Zorio, 2012).

Following Simunic (1980), the model to explain audit fees and to test the stated hypothesis presents the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned} AUDITFEES_{it} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 TRAN - FFP + \beta_2 FFP + \beta_3 NONAUDITFEES_{it} + \beta_4 TA_{it-1} \\ & + \beta_5 FOWND_{it} + \beta_6 NUMSUBSF_{it} + \beta_7 REPORTLAG_{it} + \beta_8 ROA_{it-1} \\ & + \beta_9 LEV_{it-1} + \beta_{10} LIQ_{it-1} + \beta_{11} LOSS_{it-1} + \beta_{12} GCO_{it-1} \\ & + \beta_{13} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{14} AUDITCHANG_{it} + \beta_{15} GENDER_{it} + \beta_{16} POINTS_{it-1} \\ & + \beta_{17} ATTENDANCE_{it-1} + \varepsilon_{it} \end{aligned}$$

Table 2 presents the variables included in the model. In it, there are three dummy variables to reflect the different periods under scrutiny in this paper. They are related directly to FFP. The seasons before the FFP (PRE-FFP) are considered as base. Total assets variable has been included to control for the size. Whether the owner of the club is a foreigner has been considered as a factor that can increase the audit fees. The number of subsidiaries abroad variables has been included to analyze the effect of the complexity of the audit work. Other variables have been included to analyze the impact of risk. They are ROA, leverage, liquidity, if the club had losses the previous season, and if the auditing report presented going concern opinion. The features of the auditor are included to analyze the effect of that the auditor is one of the Big4, if the change in the auditor and their gender affect the fees and if the audit fees. Finally, the possible

effect of sporting factors has been introduced in the model with the points obtained in the previous season and the average attendance to the stadium. All these variables are explained in the following pages.

Table 1. Description of the variables included in the model and expected sign.

Variables	Definition	Sign
Dependent variable		
AUDITFEES	Amount paid for auditing fees (in Euros)	
Independent variables		
PRE-FFP	1 seasons when FFP regulations were not applied (2007/08, 2008/09 y 2009/10); 0 otherwise.	
TRAN-FFP	1 seasons of transition to the full implement of the FFP (2010/11, 2011/12 y 2012/13; 0 otherwise.	+
FFP	1 seasons when FFP regulations are fully implemented (2013/14, 2014/15 y 2015/16); 0 otherwise.	+
NONAUDITFEES	Expenses on non-audit services (in Euros)	+/-
L.TA	Total Assets in previous fiscal year	+
FOWN	1 if main owner is foreign; 0 otherwise	+
NUMSUBSF	Number of subsidiary companies abroad	+
REPORTLAG	Days between the close of the accounts and the auditing report.	+
L.ROA	Return on Assets in previous fiscal year	-
L.LEV	Leverage in previous fiscal year	+
L.LIQ	Current Assets divided by Current Liabilities in previous year	-
L.LOSS	1 the club had losses in previous season; 0 otherwise.	+
L.GCO	1 of the report in previous year include going concern opinion; 0 otherwise.	+
BIG4	1 if auditor is one of the big 4 auditing companies; 0 otherwise.	+
AUDITCHANG	1 if the auditor have changed; 0 otherwise.	-
GENDER	1 if the auditor who sign the report is a woman; 0 otherwise.	+
L.POINTS	Points obtained by the club in the previous season	-
L.ATTENDANCE	Average attendance to the stadium in the previous season	-

Regulation

As it was stated, Griffin et al. (2009), Vieru & Shadewitz (2010), De George et al. (2013), De Fuentes & Sierra-Grau (2015a), Higgins et al. (2016) and Lin & Yen (2016) have analyzed the impact of changes in accountancy rules or new ones in audit fees. Menon & Williams (2001), Ghosh & Lustgarten (2006), Raghunandan & Rama (2006), Griffin & Lont (2007), Ghosh & Pawlewicz (2009), Huang et al. (2009), Salman & Carson (2009), Charles et al. (2010) and De Fuentes & Sierra-Grau (2015b) have

studied the impact of changes in auditing rules. Most of these studies distinguish two or three periods: before the application of the regulation, during the first years of implementation, and after it. This paper analyses the time before the FFP (seasons 2007/08, 2008/09 y 2009/10), a transitory period (2010/11, 2011/12 y 2012/13), and the period when the FFP has been fully implemented (2013/14, 2014/15 y 2015/16). The first period is taken as base. It is expected that the audit fees be higher after the transitory or full implementation than before the new rules. The complexity of the audit work will increase with the subsequent increment in the auditing effort. Moreover, it is expected a higher exposure of their responsibility when reporting their opinion,

Non audit fees

The studies that have tried to determine conjunctly the fees for audit and non-audit services have observed interdependency between both fees and identified the existence of efficiencies derived from the exchange of knowledge between both activities (Monterrey & Sánchez, 2007). Simunic (1984) discovered a positive association between both fees. He concluded that firms that hire non-audit services to the same auditor assume cost in the audit fees higher than those firms that do not do it. Palmrose (1986) and Bell, Landsman & Shackelford (2001) point out that the positive coefficients associated between audit and non-audit fees have their origin in the scale economies that reduce the number of hours needed for auditing. Nevertheless, other authors like Abdel-Khalik (1990), O'Keefe, Simunic & Stein (1994), Stein, Simunic & O'Keefe (1994) and Whiisenant et al. (2003) did not find direct relationship between both variables.

Size of the firm (the club)

Hay, Knechel & Wong (2006) and Hay (2013) have found that the size of the audited firm explains the audit fees. This paper use the lagged total assets of the company to avoid endogeneity. Barkess & Simmet (1994), Mennon & Willians (2001), Mayhew & Wilkins (2003), Casterella, Francis, Lewis & Walker (2004), Basioudis, Papanstantinou & Geiger (2008), Jaramillo et al. (2012) use also the total assets to control the size.

Foreign ownership

Wilson, Plumley & Ramchandani (2013) assert that foreign ownership may help clubs to improve their accounts, make them sustainable and improve their finances. At

the same time, foreign investors have more difficulties to get information than the local ones (Kang & Stulz, 1997; He, Rui, Zheg & Zhu, 2014; Beneish & Yohn, 2008). To compensate this, foreign investors will look for more qualified auditors (Dimitropoulos, 2016). So, a positive relationship is expected regarding audit fees.

Complexity

Simunic (1980), Joshi & Al-Bastaki (2000), Niemi (2002), Whisenant et al. (2003) and Nikkinen & Sahlström (2005) provide evidences that the operative complexity of the client will influence the audit fees. As much complex is a client, more difficult is the auditing process and more time for the work will be needed (Simunic 1980; Hackenbrack & Knechel, 1997). The complexity will increase if the firm has numerous subsidiaries (Simunic 1980). The location of the subsidiaries also influence the complexity. Ezzamel, Gwill & Holl (1996) y Niemi (2005) maintain that having subsidiaries abroad affect the audit fees. This paper includes the variable NUMSUBSF to reflect this level of complexity. It is expected a positive relationship with the audit fees.

On the other hand, it can be expected that if the audit work is more complex it may imply more time to be performed and the subsequent delay in the signature of the audit report. So, in that case, higher fees would be expected. For that reason, the variable REPORTLAG has been included in the model.

Delay in the report

The existence of problems can imply a longer period of time to finish the audit report (Knechel & Payne 2001). Stanley (2011) found a positive relationship between the audit fees and the time spent until the final audit report.

Risk

There is an extensive literature that comes to demonstrate that the audit fees are positively related to risk. That is, higher risk in the client can expose the auditor. Then the auditor will practice more tests increasing the time employed. For that reason the fees would be higher. There are several variables to measure direct or indirectly the risk. ROA is included because if the return on assets is low, it may be a symptom of mismanagement. So, a negative relationship is expected. Callaghan, Parkash & Singhal, (2009), Xu, Carson, Fargher & Jiang (2013), Zhang & Huang (2013), Alexeyeva & Svanström (2015) and Zaman et al. (2017) have use it.

Leverage (LEV) and liquidity (LIQ) ratios reflect if the club could have financial problems. They are two of the most commonly used proxies to measure indebtedness (Hay et al., 2006; Hay, 2013). A positive relationship between leverage and audit fees is expected (Simon & Francis, 1988; Low, Tan & Koh, 1990; Taylor & Simon, 1999; Menon & Willians, 2001; Mayhew & Wilkins, 2003; Casterella et al., 2004; Callaghan et al., 2009; Jaramillo et al., 2012). On the contrary, a negative relationship is expected with the liquidity (Simunic 1980; Craswell, Francis & Taylor, 1995).

Moreover, Simunic (1980), Low et al. (1990), Waresul & Moizer (1996), Taylor & Simon (1999), Carson, Fargher, Simon & Taylor (2004), Casterella et al. (2004), Callaghan et al. (2009), Jaramillo et al. (2012) find that firms with losses (LOSS) represent higher risk. So, the audit fees would be higher as well.

Additional risk

Football clubs have real financial difficulties in their operations (Ascari & Gagnepain, 2006; Boscá, Liern, Martínez & Sala, 2008; Barajas y Rodríguez, 2010, 2014; Kuper & Szymanski, 2009; Beech, Horsman & Magraw, 2010). It has implied in some cases bankruptcies. This creates an additional risk for the auditor that will have to pay special attention to those events that can imply going concern. It is expected that if there is a going concern opinion (Whisenant et al., 2003; Stanley, 2011; Krishnan & Wang, 2015; Wang & Chui, 2015) the audit fees be higher.

Reputation

DeAngelo (1982), Francis & Wilson (1988), and DeFond (1992) affirm that big international audit firms have the reputation that their auditing services are of higher quality than those provided by small and medium audit firms. Whisenant et al. (2003), Abbott, Parker, Peters & Raghunandan (2003), Liu (2007), Monterrey & Sánchez (2007) and Jaramillo et al. (2012) have found that big audit firms charge higher audit fees. A dummy variable have been included in the model. It differentiates between the Big 4 - Deloitte, PriceWaterhouseCoopers (PWC), Ernst & Young (EY) and KPMG – and the rest.

Change in the auditor

One of the most common reasons given by clients when decide to change the auditor is that the audit fee is going to decrease. For that reason, this kind of variable is often included when analyzing audit fees. Hay et al. (2006), Hay (2013), Charles et al. (2010),

Redmayne et al. (2010), Wang & Chui (2015) and De Fuentes & Sierra-Grau (2015a) use a dummy that reflect the change in the auditor. This paper also includes it expecting a negative relationship with audit fees.

Auditor features

Recent papers study the effect that the features of the auditor may have on the quality of the auditing service (Goodwin, 2012, Ittonen & Peni, 2012, Gul, Wu & Yang, 2013, Ittonen, Peni & Vähämaa, 2013, Sundgren & Svanström, 2014). Ittonen & Peni (2012) found that audits performed by women in Denmark, Sweden and Finland were more expensive than those performed by men. However, Alexeyeva & Svanström (2015) did not find evidences in their work about audit fees in Sweden. A variable considering the gender has been included in the model.

Sporting features

It could be expected that those teams with better performance in previous season would be able to increase revenues and reduce the financial risk of the club. In the same line, similar effect would be expected if the average attendance to the stadium is high because it reflects a wide fan base that would help to increase the revenues. If the risk is low then the audit fees should also decrease. For that reason, the variables that gather the information about points and average attendance in the previous season have been included in the model.

Data and methodology

Data selection procedure

The empirical analysis has been carried out for the football teams of the Spanish First Division. The information included in the annual accounts and their corresponding audit reports has been used. This information has been gathered from several sources: websites of football teams, Spanish Professional Football League (*La Liga*), House of Companies and Amadeus database. Therefore, the initial sample should consist of data from 20 football teams with a nine-year follow-up, for each of the seasons between 2007/08 and 2015/16. Only the first division teams have been analyzed as they have the chance of qualify to UEFA competitions (Champions League and Europa League). Finally, the data for Osasuna (2009/10 and 2012/13), Xerez (2009/10), Levante (2007/08) and Rayo Vallecano (2015/16) are missing.

The audit fees paid by Real Madrid and Barcelona are much higher on average than those paid by the rest of the clubs. This can be observed in Table 2 and Graph 1. For that reason Real Madrid and Barcelona have been treated separately to the rest.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of Audit fees for Real Madrid (RM) and Barcelona, and the rest of the clubs.

	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Rest of the clubs	155	18,502.48	9,836.13	3,705.00	50,500.00
RM and Barcelona	18	144,333.30	23,069.59	104,000.00	170,000.00

Graph 1. Differences in average of Audit fees between Real Madrid and Barcelona, and the rest of the clubs.

Previously to analyze the factors that explain the audit fees, different t-test for two samples have been carried out in order to see if there are significant differences in the different periods. As there are three periods, the comparison is between each period and the rest. This is done on the sample without Real Madrid and Barcelona.

Table 3. Two-sample t test with equal variances (pre-FFP)

Group	Obs	Mean	Std. Err.	Std. Dev.	[95% Conf. Interval]	
0	104	19293.24	1036.383	10569.07	17237.82	21348.66
1	51	16889.93	1119.547	7995.167	14641.26	19138.61
combined	155	18502.48	790.0571	9836.132	16941.73	20063.22
diff		2403.306	1675.727		-907.2433	5713.856
diff = mean(0) - mean(1)					t =	1.4342
Ho: diff = 0					degrees of freedom =	153
Ha: diff < 0		Ha: diff != 0		Ha: diff > 0		
Pr(T < t) = 0.9232		Pr(T > t) = 0.1536		Pr(T > t) = 0.0768		

There is significant difference in the audit fees in the period before the FFP being slightly lower than in the two other periods. However, in the period of transition there is no significant difference in the audit fees. Finally, the audit fees in the period of full implementation of FFP are significantly higher than in the two previous periods.

Table 4. Two-sample t test with equal variances (FFP)

Group	Obs	Mean	Std. Err.	Std. Dev.	[95% Conf. Interval]	
0	102	17269.16	822.4271	8306.107	15637.69	18900.63
1	53	20876.03	1647.176	11991.62	17570.72	24181.33
combined	155	18502.48	790.0571	9836.132	16941.73	20063.22
diff		-3606.865	1645.323		-6857.349	-356.3811
diff = mean(0) - mean(1)					t =	-2.1922
Ho: diff = 0					degrees of freedom =	153
Ha: diff < 0		Ha: diff != 0		Ha: diff > 0		
Pr(T < t) = 0.0149		Pr(T > t) = 0.0299		Pr(T > t) = 0.9851		

Results

There are some results that come to corroborate what it was expected however most of the variables do not present significant influence on audit fees. First, it has been discovered that audit fees increased in almost 2,000 Euros in the transition period comparing with the time when FFP did not exit. That amount almost double when the FFP regulations were fully implemented. This result was expected and even more after the t-test.

The foreign ownership is other significant factor that explains the audit fees. When there is a foreign investor in the club the audit fees increase almost in 5,000 Euros regarding clubs with local owners.

Table 5. Outputs of the regression

VARIABLES	Audit Fees
Transition to FFP	1,886* (1,002)
FFP	3,717*** (1,272)
Non Audit Fees	0.00155 (0.0521)
Lag Total Assets	7.39e-06 (1.33e-05)
Foreign Owner	4,984** (2,340)
Number subsidiaries abroad	946.2 (3,501)
Report delay	-14.20 (23.60)
Lag ROA	-455.8 (2,303)
Lag Leverage ratio	-345.1 (992.6)
Lag liquidity ratio	-301.5 (1,858)
Lag Losses	19.25 (892.7)
Lag Going Concern Opinion	2,003 (1,371)
Big4	13,296*** (2,606)
Auditor Change	938.8 (1,525)
Auditor Gender	4,504** (2,024)
Lag Points	-8.355 (62.80)
Lag Average Attendance	-0.0889 (0.219)
Constant	17,690** (6,995)
Clubs fix effect	YES
Observations	115
Number of id	25
R-squared	0.664

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

If the auditor is one of the Big 4 represent some 13,000 Euros more than smaller audit firms. This is in line with the previous research. It should be noted that only apart

Real Madrid and Barcelona –both excluded of this analysis- only Sevilla CF and Valencia CF were audited by a Big4 audit firm in season 2014/15 and 2015/16, and Málaga CF in season 2015/16. In those seasons, the FFP regulations were fully implemented. Moreover, Valencia CF and Málaga CF have foreign investors. On the other hand, only Ernst&Young and Deloitte –belonging to the Big4- have audited football clubs in the whole period.

Finally, when the auditor is a woman audit fees are higher in some 4,500 Euros than when the auditor is a man. This also comes to corroborate the findings of Ittonen & Peni (2012). Only one of them works for Ernst&Young.

There is no evidence that sporting factors could influence the audit fees. Maybe this is explained because there is not relationship between sports performance and economic results in Spanish football (Barajas et al., 2005). Variables related to risk have resulted to be no significant as well.

Conclusions

It have been tested that audit fees have grown after the implementation of FFP regulations. On top of that, audit fees are explained by the presence of foreign investors, if the audit firm is one of the Big4 and if the auditor is a woman.

The results of this study provide several future research lines. First, it would be interesting to analyze this considering other European leagues. Second, would be also interesting to study other effects of FFP regulations like if there have been significant changes in the auditor opinion.

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